

strong aya

A new, interdisciplinary, multi-stakeholder European network to improve healthcare services, research and outcomes for Adolescents and Young Adults with cancer.

The future of cancer therapy

YOUTH
CANCER
EUROPE

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Deliverable Report

WP4 – Operation of STRONG-AYA ecosystem, stakeholder and patient involvement, dissemination, exploitation, communication

Deliverable D4.9

First annual report on the progress and success of ecosystems.

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Description:

Annual report of the first year of operation of the Strong AYA local, national and international ecosystems.

Including a report on the methodology to assess the reliability of Strong-AYA outcomes by assessing data quality and data processing by Strong-AYA systems.

1. Publishable summary (max ½ page)**Summary:**

This document details progress over the past 12 months towards developing the appropriate infrastructure for the functioning of local, national, and a pan-European ecosystem for the generation, analysis and interpretation of data related to AYA living with or after cancer.

Deliverable D4.9 aims to describe what actions from each individual roadmap have been successfully defined and achieved to deliver our ecosystems. It also lists which actions are still to be achieved, with risks, mitigations, facilitating processes and metrics to overcome them.

We have revised some of our terminology, to refer to a clearer meaning of 'data ecosystems', and we have set ourselves a new internal metric for what we consider partly and fully national reach for our ecosystems.

Table 2, summarises the detailed findings of this report in relation to our initial objectives and details our next steps for the next 12 months, based on the status of ecosystem development at each of the three levels i.e. locally, nationally and European-wide.

Contents

1. PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY (MAX ½ PAGE)	3
2. OUR STRONG-AYA ECOSYSTEMS – DEFINITIONS AND INTERNAL METRICS	5
2.1 WHAT WE HAVE ACHIEVED ON OUR ECOSYSTEMS, IN THE LAST 12 MONTHS	10
3 METHODOLOGY TO ASSESS THE RELIABILITY OF STRONG-AYA OUTCOMES BY ASSESSING DATA QUALITY AND DATA PROCESSING BY STRONG-AYA SYSTEMS	14
3.1 TECHNICAL STANDARDS	14
3.2 ETHICAL STANDARDS	14
3.3 STANDARDS AND RULES AROUND DAY-TO-DAY OPERATIONS WITHIN THE ECOSYSTEM.....	15
3.4 RULES ON USING THE ECOSYSTEM FOR FEDERATED LEARNING AND ANALYTICS.....	15
3.5 KPIs DEFINED.....	15
3.6 MANAGEMENT OF NATIONAL AND INSTITUTIONAL DIFFERENCES.....	15
3.7 METHODOLOGY:.....	16
3.7.1 Stakeholder consultations:.....	16
3.7.2 Stakeholder interviews and surveys:.....	16
4. THE RESEARCH PRIORITIES FOR OUR ECOSYSTEMS	25
4. PLANS TO EXPAND OUR ECOSYSTEMS FROM 2025 ONWARDS	25

2. Our STRONG-AYA ecosystems – definitions and internal metrics

STRONG-AYA brings together an international multi-disciplinary consortium across seven European countries, led by the Netherlands Cancer Institute (NKI) and composed of academic research organisations (European Organisation for Research and Treatment of Cancer (EORTC), University of Southampton, University of Leeds, University of Manchester, Maastricht University, Netherlands Comprehensive Cancer Organisation (IKNL)), clinical partners (Italian National Tumour Institute, Léon Bérard Centre, Gustave Roussy Institute, Maria Skłodowska-Curie National Research Institute of Oncology, the Leeds Teaching Hospitals National Health Service Trust), stakeholder and patient organisations (Youth Cancer Europe, European Cancer Organisation) and a consulting company (FFUND).

The integral components of our Strong-AYA ecosystems are:

- 1) An inter-professional, interdisciplinary and service user community, working together and sharing knowledge, ideas, processes and information that meet the overall purposes of STRONG-AYA.
- 2) A set of local databases
 - a) To store pseudonymised individual-level patient data in a local private repository, or 'safe space' (often termed a Secure Research Environment) within the data governance structure of each partner.

Our primary purpose is not to grant external access to these data held locally. Specific pieces of statistical algorithms, generated by partners UNIMAAS and IKNL, will summarise each set of local data, and bring only the aggregated or summary-level analyses from each partner centre together forming an overall analysis.
- 3) Develop applications through which local data managers will all be able to:
 - a) Prepare, and make data FAIR inside their local ecosystem (so that they remain as data owners ethically and legally).
 - b) Examine their own data to monitor completeness and evaluate data quality (at a level of detail that fits with their permissions).
- 4) Tools (such as 'Apps') that can optimise the knowledge gained by us and others from our work to:
 - a) Run predefined analyses automatically ('in real time', 'on demand', 'on the fly') upon these data.
 - b) Build AYA-specific aspects, into (for example):
 - i) Existing research questions (EuroCare)
 - ii) Existing patient-driven questions (their websites)
 - iii) Existing policy questions (ECO)
- 5) A sophisticated web-based software application, which
 - a) Serves multiple stakeholders (e.g. clinicians, patients, policy makers) or multiple communities or related stakeholders.
 - b) Provides specific access to an appropriate layer or level of the web space, for each specific individual logging in, according to their own requirements and characteristics.

6) A design and culture that promotes co-operation and engagement, to maximise shared learning.

As the technical infrastructure and personnel taking part are only of value alongside the data they hold, we are considering amending our terminology from ‘ecosystems’ to ‘data ecosystems’. Data ecosystems around their data are currently being set up within five participating European nations. Each partner has put in place its own local ecosystem including people, skill-mix, regulatory and approval processes, local retrospective data (often with regional reach), and a plan to create its own local prospective data. The five nations are:

- The UK – with centres in Leeds and Manchester
- France – with centres in Paris and Lyon
- Italy – a centre in Milan
- The Netherlands – a centre in Amsterdam
- Poland – a centre in Warsaw

These are each aspiring to true national reach. However ‘national’ lacks precise definition in this context; much longer-standing data systems often do not have population-based national reach, for many parameters (such as cancer stage, treatment, or relapse status) and even less so for parameters we will collect (such as care received, quality of life and symptoms). Our current initiative is unlikely to rapidly achieve population coverage. Therefore, we have defined what we consider national reach for our national ecosystems, to enable us to map our progress towards that ultimate goal: In very simple operational terms we consider

- More than five clinical or population-based data sources within a nation is ‘national’.
- Two to five is ‘partly national’.
- One data source only is ‘local’.

We accept this is an interim and internal metric for ourselves, but we consider it helpful to work against, to ensure appropriate overall progress. Along with this structure to define what we feel a ‘national data ecosystem’ is, we have also worked to define a structure that characterizes local, national and international data ecosystems, to assist us in working, step by step, towards national and international reach:

Table 1

Scope	City/community-specific	Country-wide	Pan-European
Stakeholders	Local agencies, residents	National Government, NGOs	Global institutions, multinational bodies
Data sources	Local data (eg. Municipal)	National registries, surveys	Cross-border research, global databases
Challenges addressed	Context-specific issues (neighbourhood level health trends)	National priorities (eg disease prevalence)	Global challenges (eg pandemic, climate change)
Collaboration	Regional partnerships	Federal-state coordination	International coalitions

Well-developed systems and discussions to create national-reach existing AYA data access are underway in the Netherlands, France and the UK. Existing national AYA-specific PRO data is limited to the Netherlands (with multicentre national coverage) and partly national in England (with 2 centres

contributing existing PRO data and the national register providing a third source of clinical data from its AYA-onset cancer outcomes dataset, but not including PRO data). Prospective data will also be partly national in France, with PRO data from two centres.

Achieving national reach more widely is limited by:

1. Delayed engagement of national policy-makers for population-based national AYA cancer data, meaning that data availability is based upon data altruism, which is not as fast or effective as if supported by policy incentives. Were policy-makers to issue guidance that all centres with AYA practices should collect outcomes data based upon the STRONG_AYA COS, then national reach would be facilitated for prospective data. Work to achieve this policy engagement is ongoing in Netherlands, France and England.
2. Cultural and practical differences in the approach to data of various types. For example different parts of our consortium have different medical cultures in relation to the importance of AYA as a specific oncology patient group, and the importance of patient reported outcomes in clinical practice.
3. Delayed confirmation and refinement of the Core Outcome Set for Strong-AYA, resulting in
 - a. Limitations in the testing of ecosystems upon real AYA data. However, tests on dummy data have been entirely secure and effective.
 - b. Limitations in the quality assurance of the CoS data held in each location and nation.

The key cross-cutting actions for the next year of our national ecosystems are: (i) to obtain retrospective data with national reach, and (ii) to create and test a roadmap and mechanism for prospective data with national reach.

Our pan-European umbrella ecosystem will include the data from each of our 7 local ecosystems, and operate from the Netherlands. The progress of the national ecosystems is also set out in the revised deliverable 4.4 submitted September 2024.

Our actions to demonstrate our ambition of achieving truly national reach for our ecosystems is summarised below:

Table 2. Milestones towards national ecosystems

Country	Progress	Barriers	Action	Timeline	Milestone
UK	Agreement with NCRAS for data to be shared and application started	Time taken for NCRAS to process requests and provide data. No agreement for NCRAS to have their own Vantage 6 hub	Obtain retrospective epidemiology data focusing on age tumour type and survival	Winter 2024/2025	Dataset exported from NCRAS to Manchester for FL analysis
France	HORUS and UniAJA research grant processes ongoing, to collect AJA-onset cancer outcomes in multiple French AJA units.	The COS in terms of technical feasibility and data federation and evaluation of the acceptability and impact will be assessed within the timescales and context of Strong-AYA ahead of discussions with other French AYA units.	Test the feasibility and acceptability of the COS collection. Further grant application (IGR-led)	Spring 2025	Grant submitted by IGR
Italy	JANE2 launched in Autumn 2024	No national AYA or PRO collection infrastructure, lack of resource	Continue discussions within JANE2 about national federated data	Ongoing throughout programme duration	
Netherlands	Existing infrastructure is in place, with existing national data	Bureaucratic delays due to filing an amendment to existing study to collect additional STRONG AYA core outcome set not already collected as part of Dutch COMPRAYA study (anticipated January 2025)	Ethics amendments	Winter 2024/5	Data sharing confirmed in writing for secondary use in STRONG-AYA of existing COMPRAYA and SURVAYA dataset
Poland	Discussion with team at Maria Skłodowska-Curie National Research Institute of Oncology.	It is not possible to integrate national data into the programme due to national legal and IT infrastructure constraints and at a local level	Showcase the novel integration of the local PROMs data with the clinical data to provide a	Ongoing throughout the programme duration.	Integration of existing AYA cancer fertility PRO data into Vantage6 Node at Warsaw

		<p>budgets, capability and resource capacity limitations. So only core data from the centre can be provided prospectively. There is not a culture in Poland of collecting and using patient reported outcomes in clinical practice.</p>	<p>template of what is realistic and achievable for other centres to follow in the future. This could be done through presentations on Strong-AYA at national conferences, leaflets promoting the work of Strong-AYA and co-operation with advocacy and professional groups.</p>		
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2.1 What we have achieved in our data ecosystems, in the last 12 months

Discussions with each centre and accompanying questionnaires enabled us to establish the following (also detailed in D4.6):

- Through defining what the ecosystems are, we have established the general criteria that are necessary to run such ecosystems. (Milestone 2)
- The local/national situation has been characterised in specific detail for each nation, through discussions with each centre and site, and exploratory conversations about national ecosystems where applicable, including in UK and France where two local ecosystems will exist. (Milestone 3)
- The technical specifications of the local and central infrastructures have been provided in the Technical Blue Print and the Data Management Plan which have been circulated to all sites and which formed the deliverable in WP3. (Milestone 3)
- Data sources, flows, processing and recipients with actions to complete for each location have been established through ongoing work with WP1 and others.
- The legal and governance frameworks have been defined for each location, through work which was led by EORTC in WP2 and well received in each centre.
- EORTC through WP2 have led work ensuring that local ethical and legal requirements to ensure compliant data collection for the Core Outcome Set (COS) are either met or in progress.
- Local data collection and flows have been activated and data linkage and local quality assurance processes shared and understood.
- We have established that the correct personnel are in place in each centre to allow for data collection, data processing/analysis and data storage/management.
- Through our discussions and wider work with each centre, we have established whether patient and Health Care Professional (HCP) portals are already in place and where they exist what the current set-ups look like.
- We have identified the forms of existing data that are available for FAIR-ification in each partner and each clinical centre, which can be used to establish predictive modelling and validate the statistical, technical and ethical procedures we plan to complete.
- We have started to discuss with local centres the facilitators and barriers to achieving sustainability for Strong AYA in due course.
- We have begun to establish the process for certification of the local technical infrastructure, alongside WP3.
- We explored potential local cultural or systemic barriers in the development of national cancer data ecosystems. The summary of this is detailed in Table 3 below, where we specify the mitigations, methods and timed actions for overcoming the barriers.

In our discussions and questionnaires in the last 12 months, each centre has identified and delivered on individual actions needed to operate local, national and pan-European ecosystems. These actions were based upon our initial individual roadmaps for each centre, whose data will contribute to our pan European federated data ecosystem.

The roadmap provided previously (D4.6) splits the individual actions required of each beneficiary into six categories of actions, providing us with data, insights, and planning national reach.

Figure 1 Key work to be delivered in the national data ecosystems

A summary on the update of the progress of the roadmap over the last 12 months with next steps has been tabulated below.

Table 3 – Summary of our progress in overall ecosystem setup and operation over the past 12 months

Initial objectives	Progress over the past 12 months	Next Steps
Set-up local ecosystems		
Identify availability of existing relevant data	Complete across each local centre. No retrospective PRO data is available in Milan.	FAIR-ify data, pseudonymise it and make it available for federated analyses, Deadline: Spring 2025.
Assess and implement local ethical and governance regulations related to individual level access for new data generation	Assessment pursued and implementation ongoing for the generation of new data	Ethical and governance processes ongoing.
Ensure resource (technological, human) capacity and capability to pursue work in each location	Completed across most local centres.	NKI to employ a further researcher, IT staff in Milan to be recruited
Assess local aggregate level data access in appropriate secure environment in local data repositories	Create a Secure Research Environment at each location to store pseudonymised individual-level patient data in a local private repository	Data identified and due to be made available across all sites by Q2 2025
Determine availability of data in local EHRs	Completed across most sites including data flow from EHRs to repository	Data flow mapping ongoing.
Define, and progress towards generating new data	COS completed, clinical co-factors defined, ethics ongoing to start generating new data	Ethics due January 2025 across sites.
Determine availability of local clinical registry data	Local registries identified and datasets characterised	Data flows being defined. Due Q2 2025.
Ensure appropriate storage of existing and newly generated PRO data	Identify a Secure Research Environment within the data governance structure of each partner	Completed across most sites. PRO data will not be collected in Italy.
Set-up national ecosystems		
Assess national regulations related to accessing relevant data	Completed across all sites.	
Assess and adapt to ongoing international cultural differences in COS questions and data governance	This is ongoing between individual sites and Southampton.	Q3 2025

Determine and progress towards generating new data across minimum 2 organisations in a nation	This is ongoing.	
Determine availability of national-level clinical registry data	Completed	Data flows to be mapped: Q1 2025
Draw up appropriate agreements for national-level data aggregation across separate legal entities	Completed in most sites	No plans to enlarge the data collection to other legal entities except Milano within Italy at present.
Draw up storage and data storage and processing agreements for aggregated clinical outcome data	Completed in most sites	Final sites to be completed by Q2 2025
Set-up international ecosystems		
Agree installation of all appropriate hardware and software for the storage and protection of aggregate data at local/national levels	Completed in most sites	Italy expected Q2 2025
Ensure federated access to data from national/local ecosystems	Completed in most sites	Italy expected Q2 2025
Ensure a safe and appropriate level of access point for all stakeholders	Interoperability and FAIR-ification tool functionality in place across most sites	Italy expected Q2 2025
Ensure and maintain appropriate technological governance	Ongoing	This will be ongoing until the end of project
Develop and update as necessary regulations and publication of reports	Ongoing	This will be ongoing until the end of project

3 Methodology to assess the reliability of Strong-AYA outcomes by assessing data quality and data processing by Strong-AYA systems

3.1 Technical standards

Colleagues in the University of Maastricht through Work Package 3 have developed methods, plans and guidelines on data security, integrity, privacy and rules of access which each of the five participating ecosystem centres will abide by and which help to ensure standardisation throughout the project.

The Technical Blueprint (Deliverable 3.3) introduces and details the general requirements for each of the four specified cornerstones of technology:

- FAIR data principles,
- Secure infrastructure,
- Federated analytics and learning,
- Federated data ecosystems.

The plan aims to leverage existing expertise, build on top of local systems and provide support to extend and improve these systems.

The Data Management Plan (Deliverable 3.1) outlines (1) in general terms the data used in Strong-AYA (2) that this data is available for federated analysis, but protected from those not entitled to access it, by keeping it within the data-holding institutions, (3) implementation of the FAIR principles to make institutional data mutually inter-operable across the Strong-AYA consortium and (4) availability of the data after the project ends.

3.2 Ethical standards

D2.2 provides Strong-AYA with an information governance and ethics framework in the form of a Code of Conduct and sets out the following applicable frameworks, the full details of which are described in detail in the deliverable:

- Data privacy
 - Lawfulness/legal basis
 - Data minimisation
 - Purpose and storage limitations
 - Transparency/information to data subject
 - Risk assessment and preventative measures
 - Accountability
- Ethics
 - Patient consent
 - Ethics committee approval of retrospective use of data
 - Patient centred/informed ethical guidance
 - Negotiating public and private (commercial) interests in data-intensive research development

Deliverables 5.2 and 4.7 ensure an alignment of members responsibilities and that tasks are conducted and completed in line with these. This is done through the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and

success measures that have been set up in alignment with the projects aims, objectives and governing principles defined by work package 5 in deliverable 5.2 and the context and rationale for the ecosystems plus the governance model and rules of operation which are detailed in deliverable 4.7.

3.3 Standards and rules around day-to-day operations within the ecosystem

The standards and rules around the day-day operations within the ecosystem to be followed by all partners have been defined and agreed in the last 12 months, and are outlined in Deliverable 4.7. They can be summarised under the following headings:

- Rules for ongoing and new partners
- Application requirements
- Decision process
- Management of user access and usage
- Resolution of disputes and ambiguous situations
- Submission of use cases

D4.7 also defines the foundational principles and the structure for the scalability and sustainability of the project.

D4.7 has been revised after external scientific review, on 30-09-2024.

3.4 Rules on using the ecosystem for federated learning and analytics

The rules for using the ecosystems for federated learning and analysis have been described in deliverable 4.7 covering the following:

- Active contribution to the data ecosystem
- Abiding by the technical standards
- Privacy preservation
- Supporting interpretability and interoperability
- Tracking successes with KPIs
- Using the infrastructure
- Intellectual property guidelines
- Sharing of benefits – the communication and dissemination of outputs

The deliverable also details the rules for ongoing and new partners joining the consortium and the management of user access. It provides information on the submission and approval of use cases with clear criteria against which they are assessed.

3.5 KPIs defined

KPIs have been set up to ensure the project is successfully implemented and to ensure outcomes are monitored and tracked. They have been developed in line with the aims, objectives and governing principles of the project.

Deliverable 5.2 (re-submitted September 2024) details the KPIs and specifically lays out a table of short and long-term objectives for the establishment of national infrastructures and the Pan-European Infrastructure. KPIs related to stakeholder adoption and value of individuals external to the project, such as policy makers, is also discussed in the Communication Plan (Deliverable 4.3).

3.6 Management of national and institutional differences

In relation to information governance principles, the Strong-AYA Consortium acknowledges the differences between institutions and countries in their capacity, capabilities, and limitations in what

data can or cannot be used for federated learning or analyses. There is an expectation that not all countries and institutions will be able to fully meet all requirements (technical, administrative etc) and there will be gaps in policies. The ethos of a collaborative pan-European ecosystem is that these gaps can be bridged as part of the working practices. A task within the ecosystem needs to be the transparent communication and discussion of these potential differences and gaps to resolve them or to develop secondary plans to achieve explicit goals.

3.7 Methodology:

3.7.1 Stakeholder consultations:

Stakeholder consultations have taken place within the community of our ecosystem to answer any questions and to seek input on how to enhance the value of the following:

Table 4 – Stakeholder Consultations

Study aspect	Stakeholders consulted	Date of interaction
Use cases	Patient representatives Healthcare Professionals Project Partners Consortium members Policy Makers Researchers	December 2023 through online surveys
IT and Data management local support	None required based upon September 2024 actions required.	NA
Data flows into the data node	NKI CLB IGR UoM NIO UoL INT	March 2023 February 2024 April 2024 May 2024 July 2024 January 2025 To follow
Healthcare Professional and Patient portals	Healthcare Professionals Patient representatives Consortium members	September 2024 through an online workshop
Ethical guidelines and code of conduct	Strong-AYA partners	Up to September 2023 and fed into D2.2 submitted September 2023

Table 3. Details of stakeholder consultations on the status of local and national ecosystems for D4.9.

3.7.2 Stakeholder interviews and surveys:

Ecosystem centres were provided with a questionnaire and followed up with a virtual meeting to provide a comprehensive overview of the progress that has been achieved in the past 12 months and

to discuss the barriers and challenges still present. The questionnaire and discussions focused on the following questions:

1. Do you have the relevant, correct and ethically approved consents in place in your organisation for the ecosystem?
2. What type of cultural/language based challenges have you identified for people accessing information about Strong-AYA?
3. The aim is to have retrospective data available in the ecosystems by the end of September 2024. Has this data been identified and ready to be made available to Strong-AYA?
4. Has the electronic location where the data you collect will be stored been set up? Is this available for data to be input?
5. Do you have the relevant people in place to manage the ecosystem – data managers, technical staff?
6. Do you have the staff in place to recruit new patients for the PRO's and have you identified where you will recruit the patients from?
7. Have local consent forms to recruit the PRO patients been drafted or approved?
8. Do you have patient information sheets available for patients about the study?
9. What actions do you believe are outstanding to have the best local ecosystem in place?
10. Do you believe you are lacking any skills or capacity to set up the ecosystem?
11. What risks of delay or non-completion can you see locally, that might be relevant to Strong-AYA and do you have mitigation plans in place?

Based upon the questionnaires, a summary of responses has been tabulated to provides an overview of the milestones achieved across the centres towards achieving the three levels of ecosystem (local, national and international). This is detailed below and includes the next steps required which will form the basis of the actions that will be reported on in D4.10.

Table 5 – Details of centre-specific milestones achieved in the past 12 months

Ecosystem partner	Ethical approvals retrospective data	Ethical approvals prospective data	Infrastructure agreement	Availability of retrospective data in data node	Research staff capacity	Data node available	Dedicated IT hardware	IT Staff	Outstanding tasks and methods	Lead and Timelines
Lyon	No retrospective PRO data so ethical approvals not needed	Awaits the completed CoS Translation	The data processing agreement is being circulated at present.	No retrospective PRO data available.	Identified that more staff are needed to enter the data. AYA nurses are available	Vantage6 node has been connected to the central Vantage6 server at Medical Data Works	A dedicated server has been identified with support available and up to date in terms of IT security standards.	Project Managers are in place.	<p>Patient information sheets need to be made available in the local language.</p> <p>Ethics application for prospective PROs.</p> <p>Questionnaires and Protocols need to be submitted in local language.</p> <p>No PRO collection solution currently in clinical use in AYA – will use an existing local in-house platform for data collection.</p>	PIS expected to be in draft in Winter 2024/25

Ecosystem partner	Ethical approvals retrospective data	Ethical approvals prospective data	Infrastructure agreement	Availability of retrospective data in data node	Research staff capacity	Data node available	Dedicated IT hardware	IT Staff	Outstanding tasks and methods	Lead and Timelines
Instituto nazionale dei tumori	Meeting with the DPO have been conducted and agreements set for the project.	Awaits the CoS translation	The data processing agreement is being circulated at present.	No retrospective PRO data is available.	PRO data will not be collected prospectively. No new staff have been recruited until now that the COS is defined.	Not at present.	Clinical data collection will be performed in RedCap and transcoded in OMPO an internal server.	Staff are not in place and has been identified as an outstanding action.	IT and human resources staff are needed at clinical and IT level.	Staff recruitment expected Data manager starting to work from January 2025
Gustave Roussy	IRB approval has been obtained however the COS DPO needs final COS to implement the data.	No. Cannot progress without the COS translation and list of co-variables. This is now in place (December 2024) but work	The data processing agreement is being circulated at present.	Some retrospective data has been identified but final COS is needed for further progress	A clinical research associate has been recruited for 24 months to consent the patients	Vantage6 node has been connected to the central Vantage6 server at Medical Data Works	A dedicated server has been identified with support available and up to date in terms of IT security standards.	IT teams are in place to extract clinical data items automatically. Quality checked will be completed by a	Patient information sheets need to be made available in the local language. Obtaining CPP approval for the prospective data collection	PIS expected in Spring 2025

		following it is delayed						Data Manager.	There is a lack of an existing technical infrastructure to collect the PRO data. A platform exists to collect breast cancer data which may be adaptable. A new platform will be costly and will require substantial resource to set up.	
Warsaw	Yes the consents are in place for the retrospective sex-	No. Ethics approval can not be applied for until the COS is in	The data processing agreement is being circulated at present.	Source data has been identified.	Two clinics have been identified from which to recruit patients. Staff are in	Vantage6 node has been connected to the central Vantage6	Need to establish a secure research data environment to put the local data.	Staff are in place at present to manage the ecosystem. There	Patient information sheets and questionnaire need to be made available in	Ethical approval is being applied for as COS is in place –

	health project.	the local language.			place to do this.	server at Medical Data Works		is no budget to sustain the ecosystem after the project ends	the local language. Support is required from the wider consortium's expertise to collect the data in a very specific structure	
NKI	Yes the consents are in place and data has started to be moved into the Strong-AYA node.	The application was sent in July 2024.	The MDW agreement has been signed. The data processing agreement is being circulated at present for all parties to sign.	Retrospective data from COMPRAYA and SURVAYA have been identified and work has started to move COMPRAYA data into the node	Access to patients is in place due to the COMPRAYA study. Applying for secondary use of the COMPRAYA data for the prospective patients.	Vantage6 node has been connected to the central Vantage6 server at Medical Data Works	Yes a server has been identified. However a dedicated server is being sourced for the longer term.	All staff in place except a Data Manager who will be recruited imminently.	Submit amendment for retrospective data to include prospective data. Draft Patient Information Sheets Seek long-term server solution for FL projects.	Since the COS is defined December 2024 this is nearing completion Early 2025 No available timeline

									Recruit A Data Manager Add data to lakehouse at and ensure the data is made FAIR for interoperability	Early 2025 Early 2025
The Christie	Not yet, UNIMASS are in discussions about the metadata structure.	The work is being led by UoL and is ongoing.	The infrastructure is already in place and has been used on another federated data analysis project previously. The data processing agreement is being circulated at present.	The retrospective data has not yet been made available. Discussions are ongoing with UNIMASS.	Data Managers are in place however staff to recruit patients will be put in post when the HRA approval has been granted.	Vantage6 node has been connected to the central Vantage6 server at Medical Data Works	An existing UKCAT infrastructure is in place.	IT staff are in post.	HRA approval has not been given yet for the prospective data collection. National Data ecosystem ongoing discussions.	Recruitment will be in place once HRA approval given HRA approval awaited January 2025 September 2027
University of Leeds	The retrospective clinical	Work is ongoing to finalise the	The data processing agreement is	The retrospective data is	The staff are all in place for	Vantage6 node installed		Dedicated IT staff are in place.	A manual check of the retrospective	HRA approval is expected

	<p>data has the approvals in place and the retrospective PRO data is being individually checked to ensure secondary use of data permission has been given.</p>	<p>documentation needed to submit the UK-specific ethics application. Sponsor approval sought, and comments responded to September 2024. Some elements are outstanding for the relevant approvals awaiting the final CoS</p>	<p>being circulated at present.</p>	<p>not available in the node however the retrospective data has been identified and work is underway to move it across.</p>	<p>the management of the ecosystems and the recruit new patients.</p>	<p>January 2025</p>			<p>the PRO studies to ensure ethics approval present for secondary use of the data. Ethics approval for prospective data collection. The final migration to the TRE server. Further investigation into how to reach less well served populations through translated questionnaires and availability in alternate formats</p>	<p>in January 2025</p>
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Table 6 Infrastructure status update

	Gustave Roussy	Centre Leon Berard	Instituto nazionale dei tumori	University of Leeds	The Christie Hospital Manchester	Netherlands Cancer Institute	Narodowy Instytut Onkologii
Nation	France		Italy	UK		Netherlands	Poland
Data station created	✓	✓	Expected 2025	✓	✓	✓	✓
Service user agreement with secure connectivity provider (Medical Data Works)	✓	✓	Expected 2025	✓	✓	✓	✓
Tested end-to-end encrypted federated query	✓	✓	Expected 2025	✓	✓	✓	✓
Tested connectivity with secure connectivity provider passed	✓	✓	Expected 2025	✓	✓	✓	✓
Tested interoperability/FAIRification tool functionality	✓	✓	Expected 2025	✓	✓	✓	✓

Table 6. Technological infrastructure status at national levels, building towards a pan-European infrastructure.

4. The Research Priorities for our ecosystems

Key questions that participants wish to use the Strong-AYA data for were identified during the initial consultations during 2023. These research priorities have progressed to form the initial Use Cases.

The top three use cases have been identified as:

1. What proportion of AYA patients had a Multi-Disciplinary Team clinical evaluation of their case prior to commencing clinical treatment/management
2. Did the patient experience psychological problems during and after treatment?
3. What proportion of AYA cancer patients survive at 1, 3, 5 years post-treatment?

The methods and processes used to establish the use cases were outlined previously (Deliverable 4.8.). In the next 12 months, with WP2, we propose to test these and other use cases against novel ethical data frameworks, to ensure our work is delivered with optimal proactive consideration of data security and ethical pitfalls.

5. Plans to expand our ecosystems from 2025 onwards

The Cancer Mission 01-05 call was for survivorship research when cancer is diagnosed in AYA aged 15-39 years. Two proposals were submitted led by STRONG-AYA beneficiaries, which included creating new datasets for use within the Strong-AYA ecosystem. These applications for the call would seek to build upon and expand the existing STRONG AYA